

Deliverable D5.4 – Formulation, consolidation and scaling up the eight LRTs

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AFFS	Adaptation funding and financing solution
CCC	Climate City Contract
EIB	European Investment Bank
EUNLRT	European network of Local Resilience Taskforce
FIE	Financing and investment entity
GT-FACC	Local Working Group on Climate Change Adaptation Finance
IC	Investment concept
IM	Incentive Mechanisms
IP	Investment plan
IS	Investment strategy
LRT	Local Resilience Taskforce
MEL	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning
PA	Public authority
PPP	Public-private partnership
SMEs	Small and medium enterprises
T	Task
WP	Work Package

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report (Deliverable 5.4) presents the consolidation and scaling of Local Resilience Taskforces (LRTs) as key mechanisms for advancing bankable climate resilience solutions across Europe. Developed under the CLIMATEFIT project, this deliverable documents how eight established LRTs are operationalizing the project's strategic objectives while creating transferable models for climate adaptation financing.

The report demonstrates how LRTs serve as innovative platforms that translate climate resilience planning into practical bankable solutions. By bringing together public authorities, financial institutions, and private sector actors, among other stakeholders, these taskforces are breaking down traditional governance barriers to adaptation financing and implementation. The consolidation process in the pioneering territories of Flanders, Strasbourg, Brescia and Alba Iulia is working to develop governance models and financing approaches, while scaling activities in Portugal, Spain, Slovenia and Czech Republic are testing their adaptability across different policy, governance and market contexts.

Central to this work are the threefold strategic objectives of 1) consolidating proven approaches through stakeholder engagement and capacity building; 2) scaling successful models to further EU territories through tailored replication strategies; and 3) ensuring transferability by developing standardized yet flexible implementation tools. These efforts contribute directly to CLIMATEFIT's overarching goal of creating bankable climate resilience solutions by demonstrating how to structure investable adaptation projects and mobilize diverse financial sources.

The LRT development process follows a co-design approach tailored to each territory, meaning their evolution does not follow a single trend. This deliverable summarizes the efforts made by all eight territories to launch and consolidate their LRTs. These activities are presented in Chapter 3 and will be further detailed in Deliverable D5.1, "Guidelines to Create and Expand the LRT."

Additionally, the European Network of Local Resilience Taskforces (EUNLRT) is introduced as a platform for knowledge sharing and peer-to-peer learning across EU regions. The first edition of the webinar series showcased the experience of LRT consolidation in the Flanders region. Insights on stakeholder engagement, financial instrument design, and governance configurations are being systematically captured to inform both ongoing implementation and future replication.

As CLIMATEFIT advances toward completion, this deliverable lays the groundwork for institutionalizing the LRT model beyond the project lifecycle. The forthcoming finalization of implementation guidelines (D5.1) and strategic connections with ongoing EU initiatives will help secure the legacy of this work, ensuring its continued contribution to mainstreaming climate adaptation financing across Europe. These efforts will be further supported by the two consolidation workshops planned for 2025 and 2026 in each territory, which will co-design roadmaps to sustain each LRT beyond the project, as well as by the continuation of the EUNLRT webinar series.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and scope of D5.4

CLIMATEFIT assists in the development and real-world application of Investment Concepts (ICs), Incentive Mechanisms (IMs), and Adaptation Funding and Financing Solutions (AFFSs). These are tested locally by Public Authorities (PAs) and key stakeholders, particularly public and private Financing and Investment Entities (FIEs), all collaborating through Local Resilience Taskforces (LRTs).

This document captures the formulation, consolidation and scaling up of eight LRTs, following the Local Resilience Taskforce model, to advance climate resilience financing at a regional and local scales through a systemic and catalytic approach. The scaling process builds on the engagement of stakeholders in the four pioneer LRTs across Italy (Brescia), France (Strasbourg), Belgium (Flanders), and Romania (Alba Iulia).

The next phase focuses on strengthening four additional LRTs in Portugal, Slovenia, and the Czech Republic, supporting public authorities in finalizing investment strategies and co-producing investment plans. *Due to resource constraints faced by the Spanish Facilitator and respective public authorities, the Spanish LRT has not been developed. Instead, further efforts have been dedicated to the Slovenian LRT, given additional adaptation investment planning activities taken by the public authority Municipality of Selnica ob Dravi.* Additionally, new cities from each CLIMATEFIT region will have the opportunity to join training workshops, fostering further growth of the LRT network across Europe.

2.2 LRT Concept and Strategic Rationale

Climate adaptation demands locally tailored solutions, as its impacts are often highly context specific. Public Authorities, positioned at the forefront of this challenge, face the dual responsibility of implementing adaptive measures and securing the necessary finance. Recognizing this, the CLIMATEFIT project develops innovative methodologies to empower PAs in diversifying their financial strategies—moving beyond traditional funding mechanisms to unlock new investment pathways. At the heart of this approach are the LRTs, which serve as collaborative platforms to bridge gaps between adaptation strategies and financeable adaptation solutions.

2.2.1 Definition and role of Local Resilience Taskforces (LRTs)

LRTs are facilitated multi-stakeholder engagement platforms established under the CLIMATEFIT project to support interaction, debate and discussion between different entities (PAs, public and private FIEs, public agencies, utilities, etc.). They aim to foster engagement in climate adaptation financing, particularly from the private sector.

They serve as an experimental arena bringing together various stakeholders to co-design, test and deploy innovative adaptation financing and funding processes and solutions through social innovation. Defined by Cajaiba-Santana's (2014) as new social practices created from collective, goal-oriented actions aimed at promoting change through reconfiguring how social goals are accomplished."

Figure 1 : Stakeholder types involved in LRTs

Key Functions of LRTs:

- **Stakeholder Coordination:** LRTs provide a structured forum for regional and local actors to align priorities, share knowledge, and co-develop adaptation strategies. They can host diverse activities (networking, consultation on local adaptation projects, capacity building, etc.).
- **Facilitating Access to Finance:** One of the core roles of LRTs is to bridge the gap between adaptation project promoters and financial institutions. By creating a dedicated space for dialogue between public authorities and FIEs—who often lack opportunities to interact directly—LRTs aims to help address the disconnect between local financial needs and the offers of financial actors. This process enhances mutual understanding and improves the design of investable/bankable adaptation project pipelines.
- **Investment Pipeline Development:** They support the transition from adaptation planning to concrete investment cases by identifying bankable and investable projects and securing financing.
- **Testing Innovative Solutions:** LRTs serve as testing grounds for new financial mechanisms, incentive models, and financial instruments for climate adaptation.

As technical collaborative platforms, LRTs play a critical role in operationalizing CLIMATEFIT’s research outcomes, ensuring that adaptation finance is effectively integrated into local and regional decision-making processes.

2.2.2 The catalytic and systemic financing approach of LRTs

The LRTs are central to CLIMATEFIT’s mission, serving as both operational engines for stakeholder collaboration and platforms for social innovation. By combining a systemic (integrated, multi-stakeholder) and catalytic (finance-

mobilizing, replicable) approach with intentional collective action, the project embodies the previously mentioned concept of social innovation by Cajaiba-Santana's (2014).

This dual approach ensures climate adaptation financing becomes scalable, sustainable, and complementary to climate adaptation strategies and plans across Europe while actively transforming local and regional governance models.

The LRT model, defined in the report "D4.5. "LRT informally established for relevant territories", fosters this social innovation by:

- Creating new collaborative practices between public, private and financial stakeholders
- Reconfiguring traditional approaches to adaptation finance through collective problem-solving
- Establishing novel governance structures for climate-resilient investment

This paradigm shift moves beyond enhancing project bankability to fundamentally transforming how climate adaptation is financed - replacing fragmented efforts with coordinated, strategic frameworks that institutionalize these innovative social practices. The consolidation of LRTs across Europe represents both a financial and social innovation milestone, creating replicable models for collective climate action that reconfigure traditional institutional boundaries and stakeholder relationships. Figure 2, shows the social innovation practices involved in the creation and facilitation of Local Resilience Practices support a systemic approach to climate funding and financing, and spur the creation of various form of value for local authorities and their stakeholders.

As a space for collaborative and innovative design of adaptation funding and financing plans & solutions, LRTs could create multiple value to local authorities and their stakeholders.

Figure 2 : Value creation of social innovation (Source: adapted from European Network of Living Labs. (2025) living Lab origins, developments, and future perspectives. Living Labs – ENoLL)

2.3 LRT Stakeholders and Engagement

This section outlines the stakeholder engagement framework for Local Resilience Taskforces (LRTs), as developed in CLIMATEFIT's Report D4.5: "LRT Informally Established for Relevant Territories." LRTs serve as collaborative platforms to drive climate adaptation finance by integrating diverse stakeholders across governance levels.

2.3.1 Stakeholder composition

LRTs unite diverse stakeholders, including PAs, FIEs, Non-Governmental organizations (NGOs), developers, utilities, and civil society to co-design climate adaptation funding and financing solutions.

LRTs are initiated, owned and managed by local and regional authorities and supported by their facilitators.

Stakeholders can only join the LRT upon invitation from the PA, the facilitator, or existing members of the LRT. Stakeholders are engaged gradually, based on existing connections with the PA and the facilitator, as well as their role in adaptation planning, funding, and financing.

Stakeholders are engaged in the LRT through engagement activities (workshops, training, outreach campaigns, FIE Champion recruitment, agreements, etc.).

Each group of stakeholders contribute uniquely to the LRT and to leveraging adaptation finance, for instance:

- The PA and the facilitator identify relevant stakeholders, involve them to join the LRT, define the taskforce's primary objectives, and coordinate the administrative matters of the LRTs.
- Other public stakeholders (regional/local governments and authorities, agencies, utilities, etc.) build their capacity in adaptation financing, align their priorities, share their knowledge, and jointly develop adaptation strategies.
- FIEs (public/private banks, insurers, institutional investors) catalyze private investment, propose financial instruments, and integrate climate risks into decision-making.
- Businesses (Small and medium enterprises - SMEs to multinationals) deliver adaptation solutions via Public-private partnership (PPPs) and resilient operations.
- Civil society ensures equitable outcomes by safeguarding community interests.

The LRTs' stakeholders are not all evenly committed. Several subgroups can be identified. The core team, a closed group, remains stable during the project lifetime, and has the advantage of allowing members to get to know each other well and build strong relationships. Other stakeholders are then integrated during the progressive development of the LRT, notably the FIEs, with a smaller degree of involvement.

The LRT core team gathers mainly public stakeholders, within the PA or its closest partnering public entities. This group allows the alignment of adaptation finance strategies at the PA level, across departments and/or agencies concerned with climate-related issues (e.g. water management, roads, urban planning, health, etc. - departments).

Figure 3: Gradual involvement of stakeholders within LRTs

2.3.2 Importance of working across scales

LRTs operationalize CLIMATEFIT's engagement strategy by bridging city-to-region scales, ensuring alignment between local adaptation needs and broader investment strategies. The phased approach—launching, expanding, and sustaining LRTs—adapts to local governance contexts while maintaining a replicable framework across regions.

Given that climate adaptation is inherently cross-sectoral and closely tied to local development planning, it requires anticipating climate impacts while mobilizing a wide range of actors across different governance levels. Local authorities frequently rely on both technical expertise and financial resources from supra-local entities, such as regional administrations, development agencies, environmental authorities, and water agencies.

In this context, interactions across governance levels often precede the formal establishment of LRTs. However, once established, LRTs play a catalytic role in structuring these interactions by focusing on adaptation and adaptation finance-related topics, helping stakeholders converge around shared priorities, investment pathways, and governance mechanisms.:

Key steps within this process include:

- Foundational engagement with core stakeholders (e.g., PAs, anchor FIEs).
- Strategic expansion to include utilities, businesses, and NGOs for investment structuring.

- Long-term institutionalization to embed adaptation financing into regional governance.

This multiscale, multi-actor model, tested in leader territories (Belgium, Romania, France, Italy), leverages social innovation—reconfiguring traditional practices through collective action (Cajaiba-Santana, 2014)—to transform adaptation finance from fragmented projects into systemic, bankable pipelines.

3 Consolidation and Scaling-Up Process

3.1 Overview of the 8 LRTs

As described in the previous section, CLIMATEFIT aims to create and sustain 8 LRTs across Europe. The first four have been created within WP4 *“Pilot solutions on 4 leader territories”* in the four lead regions of the project: Belgium, France, Romania and Italy. 4 others were planned in Portugal, Slovenia, Czech Republic and Spain as part of WP5 *“Upscale, replication and exploitation”* of LRTs.

T5.1 supports the consolidation of all 8 LRTs and will identify success factors to sustain them beyond the project and support replication.

As a reminder, LRTs are the place where the collaborative development of investment strategies (ISs), investment plans (IPs) and investment cases (ICs) will happen. According to the difference in maturity of adaptation finance matters within the PAs at each stage of the CLIMATEFIT methodology process, the LRT format and members are expected to evolve over time.

The fast-track mechanism developed by Actierra and Ramboll in WP2 *“Build capacities, project pipeline and resilient investment strategies”* is based on the assumption that IS development benefits from collective intelligence and design thinking. As such, developing investment strategies was the first activity undertaken by the core team of each LRT to foster a collective dynamic and to experiment with working together toward financing and funding adaptation solutions. Investment planning and investment concepts will be developed following the same principles, each step fostering a deeper engagement from stakeholders.

Below, a synthetical representation of this evolution presents 3 main steps, that will be adapted according to the local context. The figure below is an updated version of Figure 3, based on evidence from the leader territories. Indeed, as the LRT evolves, Ramboll has concluded that rather than enlarging the original core team, new stakeholder groups are created, interact with the core team but never completely mix. It can be seen as a barrier for social innovation, but it is more realistic considering the strategic decision to engage stakeholders around specific investments concepts and adaptation projects. The LRT core team tends to have a more strategic role.

Figure 4 Fast-track mechanism for IS, IP and IC development simultaneously with LRT development (source: CLIMATEFIT D4.5 LRTs informally established for relevant territories)

3.1.1 Short profile of each region and LRT status:

CLIMATEFIT territories are presented in Figure 5, one LRT is planned per region:

- Group 1 LRTs have been created in the lead case territories: Romania, Italy, Belgium and France
- Group 2 LRTs have been created in strategists and planners territories: Portugal, Slovenia, Czech Republic.

The Spanish LRT has unfortunately not been able to develop as planned due to a lack of capacities and resources from Spanish partners. They exited the project and the Selnica ob Dravi municipality is upgrading to planner. .

Figure 5 CLIMATEFIT Territories (Source: D1.1 Adaptation Investment Landscape, CFIT)

3.1.1.1 Italy, France, Belgium, Romania (linked to T4.1)

The 4 lead LRTs are the first ones that have been created within the project as part of T4.1. Ramboll has been leading activities in LRT definition and stakeholders' engagement to support LRT development within each region. Detailed description of each LRT is available in D4.5 "LRTs informally established for relevant territories". This data will be completed by October 2025 with an overview of the 4 leader LRTs based on summer meeting planned by Ramboll, and an overview of the 4 other LRT based on update meetings planned in September 2025 by Actierra.

Italy

The municipality of Brescia has the decision power and coordinates the LRT. Eventually, the objective is to include LRT activities inside the adaptation working group of Brescia's Air and Climate Plan. The LRT operates at municipal level, however small municipalities within the city area that participate with Brescia in other working groups might be involved in the future.

The objective of Brescia LRT is to identify new financing instruments to implement adaptation projects by working on the IS, IP and ICs. These CLIMATEFIT activities will prepare adaptation actions outlined in the work-in-progress Air and Climate Plan. In addition, the LRT will focus on the identification of local stakeholders that could be involved in LRT activities and in the investment cases.

IS and IP development have been the main activities planned for the Italian LRTs with regular meeting of the LRT core team to design the content of the IS. At this point, the LRT core team includes the PA's department of urban regeneration and the green and environmental sustainability departments. No FIEs are involved yet. Brescia is benefiting from the help of an external consultant, in charge of drafting the "Adaptation section" of the ongoing Plan for Air and Climate.

IP development, in its early phases as of the production of this report, is the opportunity to push forward the inclusion of a broader spectrum of stakeholders, especially FIEs.

France

The Eurometropole de Strasbourg (gathering the City of Strasbourg and 32 neighbouring local authorities) and the Strasbourg Climate Agency coordinate the LRT together, in order to mobilise their respective know-how, networks and skills as effectively as possible. The area covered by the Strasbourg LRT matches the metropolitan territory. The LRT has been renamed "*Local Working Group on Climate Change Adaptation Finance*" (GT-FACC).

The objective set for the GT-FACC so far is to better coordinate climate adaptation funders and financiers and to examine in depth the issues involved in financing local adaptation projects. To achieve this, the LRT focuses on the following points:

- Mapping the players and public and private financing and investment solutions for local adaptation projects.
- Identification of a list of structuring regional adaptation projects in the Eurometropole de Strasbourg

- Experimenting with new financing and investment models for regional adaptation projects
- Better estimate the funding needs of the territory
- Strengthen the stakeholders' capacity to understand the solutions and issues involved in financing adaptation.
- Promote the expertise of local and regional players on the challenges of financing adaptation to climate change at European level.

The consortium meeting held in Strasbourg in June 2025 has been the opportunity for the French LRT to invite both CLIMATEFIT stakeholders and external national stakeholders to a one-day event.

The LRT core team includes:

- the Department of finance/budget and the department of climate of Eurometropole de Strasbourg,
- the public FIE "Banque des territoires",
- the regional unit of France's national Environmental Agency ADEME
- the Grand Est Region
- A federation of financial players for sustainable development, IFD
- A public think-tank focusing on climate economics matters, I4CE (Institute for Climate Economics)

The next LRT meeting is planned in October to prepare and present investment cases.

Belgium

The Flemish government is responsible for the LRT's leadership. The latter covers the entire Flanders region (300 local cities and municipalities).

LRT's main objectives are as follows:

- Contributing to the IS, IP, ICs;
- Providing input and suggestions to the work form/organization/structure/approach of the LRT;
- Actively maintaining a network and getting in touch with new potential stakeholders for investment cases;
- Gaining recognition to attract potential stakeholders who want to participate in ICs.

After designing the IS, the LRT is currently focusing in developing IP modules with the support of Innofins and BitaGreen. The Core team of the LRT is based on the Flander's department of spatial planning, the University of Antwerp and the FIE Embuild Vlaanderen.

The IP development is an opportunity to push forward FIE engagement, supported by Embuild, and targeting banking sectors and insurers.

Romania

Alba Iulia, with the support of ALEA (Facilitator), manages the local LRT. For the time being, the LRT works at the local level. All LRT operating costs must be covered by the CLIMATEFIT project budget allocation. After the CLIMATEFIT project, additional financial sources will further be identified.

The aim of the LRT, in addition to working on IS, IP, ICs, is to focus on experience sharing and learning from best practices and concrete climate projects.

The Romanian LRT is currently focusing in engaging FIEs, by presenting the IS for feedback and assess the possibility to engage them regarding IP and IC development.

The core team of the LRT includes the program, finance, and technical departments of Alba Julia municipality. FREE (public FIE) is also involved, as well as another public stakeholder, IRCEM.

3.1.1.2 Portugal, Spain, Slovenia, Czech Republic

The second wave of LRT includes LRTs created within planners territories as part of T5.1. A series of meeting is planned in September 2025 to support LRT planning, following the methodology created by Ramboll in T4.1. As we applied the fast-track mechanism for IS development to each territory in WP2, we are currently checking the potential to develop other LRTs in strategist territories as well, or to integrate them in existing regional LRTs.

Spanish case studies are excluded from this study due to a lack of engagement from Spanish stakeholders.

Portugal :

As a EU Mission City, Porto has already established a Transition Team coordinated by the Climate Neutrality Directorate. This team was formed to develop and oversee the implementation of the Climate City Contract (CCC) and includes representatives from various municipal departments, municipal companies, Porto Energy Agency, and intermunicipal transport operators.

In the context of CCC implementation, the Transition Team has been actively meeting and has been assigned a dedicated European Investment Bank (EIB) representative who is working closely with the municipality to secure finance for climate-related initiatives.

Additionally, Porto has a Climate City Pact signed by 277 institutions, further reinforcing its commitment to climate action. Given these existing structures, establishing an LRT can be seen as redundant and risk duplicating efforts.

The investment strategy has been developed while soliciting those existing infrastructures, the core team is based on the transition team. The goal of Porto LRT is now to identify the mechanism that will allow climate finance to exist as a specific topic of interest within existing working groups. The LRT planning efforts will focus on this from the IP development.

Concerning the two strategists' territories, AdPorto is considering working on a secondary LRT bringing together stakeholders from both municipalities. Considering the lack of local resources, the core team that designed both IS will face challenges in maintaining itself.

Slovenia

The municipality of Maribor has been engaged and is interested in developing an LRT, a lot of effort and resources from Energap have been made to launch the LRT in the first semester of 2025. A launching meeting has been organized to gather the core team of stakeholders: PAs representatives and regional development agency representatives. One bank has been engaged as well.

Concerning the three strategists territories, Energap is considering supporting the development of one working group on climate finance to mutualize experiences. Due to lack of resources, this group would not be an LRT per se, but it is a first step towards consolidating climate finance expertise among three small municipalities. As Selnica ob Dravi is upgrading to a planner territory over Summer 2025, we will be discussing the opportunity to push forward the creation of an LRT to support IP development.

Czech Republic

Due to time constraints, activities regarding LRT development have not started in itself as of the production of this report. The core team has been identified to develop the investment strategy, but it has not been formalized as an LRT. We will be working together with Enviros in August-September 2025 to provide a detailed LRT implementation plan that will formalize this engagement and the launching of LRT.

3.2 Consolidation Support Activities

As part of WP4, Ramboll developed an LRT planning framework that has been applied to the four lead territories. This process will be applied to Portugal, Czech Republic and Slovenia territories by the end of September 2025.

Several tools have been developed to follow up on both IS and LRT development, several solutions have been implemented to find the right balance between monitoring and overloading facilitators.

A dashboard to monitor IS development and LRT development has been created at first, to follow up on the methodology applied to lead cases. However, it has not represented a good communication canal. The dashboard has been difficult to fill and was redundant with other tools developed in other WPs.

	SLOVENIAN PAs	PORTUGUESE PAs
Implementation status	Launch of LRT in 3 small municipalities Selnica, Lovrenc and Radlje – join event on 12th of February	
LRT activities organized so far	Launching event	
Core team stakeholders	PAs representatives and regional development agency representative	
Main challenges faced	Motivation of the PAs to be engaged in preparation of IS as well as LRT – understanding how the IS could be useful for them (there is no practice in Slovenia of preparing investment strategies at municipal level)	<p>As a Mission City, Porto has already established a Transition Team coordinated by the Climate Neutrality Directorate. This team was formed to develop and oversee the implementation of the Climate City Contract (CCC) and includes representatives from various municipal departments, municipal companies, Porto Energy Agency, and intermunicipal transport operators.</p> <p>In the context of CCC implementation, the Transition Team has been actively meeting and has been assigned a dedicated EIB representative who is working closely with the municipality to secure funding for climate-related initiatives.</p> <p>Additionally, Porto has a Climate City Pact signed by 277 institutions, further reinforcing its commitment to climate action.</p> <p>Given these existing structures, establishing an LRT can be seen as redundant and risk duplicating efforts.</p> <p>Maia is considering establishing a Climate Council as part of its ongoing Maia Climate Action Plan. This initiative aligns with the concept of a Local Resilience Taskforce; however, its development will take time and may not align with the CLIMATEFIT timeline.</p> <p>Matosinhos has internally identified key departments, units, and municipal companies involved in climate action for the development of their SECAP. However, no FIEs have been engaged in the process.</p>
Actions to overcome challenges	Shorter meeting focusing also on municipalities needs	

Figure 6 LRT implementation dashboard - February 2025

T4.4 in particular has developed a monitoring tool (MEL) that required consistent and detailed update from facilitators. To avoid overloading facilitators with redundancy, Actierra, Ramboll and Ambit are, as of the production of this report, coordinating to better define which monitoring tool is the most efficient.

CLIMATEFIT 		LOCAL RESILIENCE TASKFORCE MEL LRT Establishment					
	Description	Indicator	Means of Verification	Responsible	Target	Results	Deadline
Goal	To establish an LRT according to Ramboll conceptualization	LRT launch event	-	Facilitator PA	Carry out a launch event	Yes	28/02/2025
Activities	Stakeholder mapping	N° of external stakeholder identified	Stakeholder map	Facilitator PA	7	5	31/01/2025
	Outreach campaigns	Participants/Invitations ratio	Sent emails	Facilitator PA	100%	1	10/02/2025
Outputs	Stakeholder map analysis	Categorization of stakeholders according to Ramboll's suggested SH Framework (see LRT Engagement Strategy)	Stakeholder map	Facilitator PA	Yes	Yes	31/01/2025
	Definition of LRT's shared vision (Ramboll's conceptual framework)	Completion of the framework	-	Facilitator PA	Vision framework completed and agreed upon by all participants.	Yes	28/02/2025
		Number of reviews completed out of the planned reviews	-		N/A		15/06/2025
Outcomes	Creation of a core LRT team	N° of stakeholder involved	LRT's Core team members list	Facilitator PA	5	4	10/02/2025
	Creation of a diverse working group that includes relevant stakeholders (step 2&3)	Diversity of stakeholders involved (FIEs, Public entities, NGOs, Private Sector)	Attendance Sheet	Facilitator PA	1	1	15/06/2025
		N° of external stakeholder involved			0	0	15/06/2025

Figure 7 Extract from the monitoring tool for LRT establishment - Selnica ob Dravi municipality

As the monitoring tool requires extensive work, the methodology has been simplified (see D4.6 Workshop for LRT) and a series of bilateral meetings has been organised in May 2025 with group 2 facilitators to replicate the monitoring process. Actierra and Ambit organised these meetings together to collect information. The meeting agenda was based on the three main elements of the MEL:

- The establishment of the Local Resilience Taskforce.
- The co-design of the Investment Strategy according to the CMCC methodology and the 'Fast-track Mechanism' (Mechanism (developed for the first 4 Investment Strategies and applied to the 13 others) developed by ACTIERRA and RAMBOLL under T2.4.
- The engagement among the participants of the LRT.

A 2025 summer update for leader LRTs has been coordinated by Ramboll to close T4.1 and formalize the start of T5.1. The goal of these bilateral meetings is to identify the challenges and update the status of the LRT. These meetings will be continued under T5.1 and extended to the Portuguese, Slovenian and Czech facilitators.

The most efficient communication channels for now are:

- the monthly update by email or during WP meeting (WP2 meeting then WP3 meeting where all facilitators are gathered).
- Bilateral meetings every 2 to 3 months to collect information, challenges and return of experience.

As mentioned previously, communicating efficiently with facilitators has been a challenge in itself. We are currently working towards the optimization of those communication channels to avoid overloading facilitators: a common tool between WP4 and WP5, common update from all WPs, common bilateral meeting when needed.

3.2.1 Regional LRT workshops

T5.1 will propose 2 consolidation workshops in each of the 8 project's regions: the first one to share guidance to upscale investment strategies into investment plans and budget planning, and the second to provide guidelines for the upscale and improved budget planning into investment cases.

3.2.1.1 Workshop 1 (M24): Guidance on upscaling investment strategies to investment plans and budget planning

The first workshop initially planned for M22 has been delayed to M24 due to IS development delays. The workshop implementation has been thought into two steps: the first one with lead cases and the second one with the others. Each facilitator has the choice to conduct the workshop online or on-site.

The workshop aims to answer the three following questions:

- What activities (interviews, meetings, workshops, data collection) are needed to complete each IP module and IC development?
- When should those activities take place and how long should module last to be completed?

- Which stakeholders should be involved in the LRT at which step of IP and IC development?

Actierra provided an agenda and supporting materials and instructed facilitators to conduct the consolidation workshop in the local language. EnviroS and Ramboll have been included in the definition of the agenda in order to make sure that it fits the state of progress of IP development.

The goal of the workshop is for participants to co-design a roadmap for LRT activities in the following month to reach CLIMATEFIT goals, and to take the first steps into sustain LRT beyond the project.

In order to adapt to every context, facilitators were encouraged to implement the consolidation workshop during another activity if they already had some planned. For Slovenian, Czech, and Portuguese LRT, the workshop is the first step towards IP development after the delivery of their IS in July 2025. Bilateral meetings with each facilitator are planned in September to clarify the objectives and goals of the consolidation workshop if needed and update the status of implementation.

Actierra provided an agenda and supporting materials on a Miro Board accessible to each facilitator.

Table 1 Proposed agenda for the consolidation workshop #1

Time	Activity
10'	Introduction: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Status progress of the LRT - Status progress of CLIMATEFIT activities
20'	Defining LRT Activities & Objectives for the next steps of CLIMATEFIT <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For each IP module, identify required activities and their goal - Include IC development - Identify activities that the LRT could take on beyond CLIMATEFIT
20'	Timeline Planning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify milestones for each module: start, finish, highlight - Identify activities outside of CLIMATEFIT that could be relevant for LRT development
20'	Stakeholder Mapping <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify the stakeholders needed for each task - Identify when they should be contacted and how to reach the goal
10'	Conclusion and planning of the next meeting

Figure 8 Consolidation workshop instructions #1

As of the conclusion of this report, only the Italian LRT conducted their consolidation workshop. Romania workshop is planned for early September, as well as France. The Flanders region is producing a roadmap for IP and will require a tailored approach. Facilitators from other territories have been contacted and are planning the workshop for September.

A full analysis of consolidation workshops will be included in D5.1, planned for September 2026.

3.2.1.2 Workshop 2 (M30): Guidelines to convert budget planning into investment cases

The second consolidation workshop is planned for February 2026. Actierra would intend to run an on-site event for each territory, providing an agenda and supporting materials. This event would be the opportunity for territory to invite a broader range of stakeholders and highlight the work done so far in CLIMATEFIT. It would also be the opportunity to involve replicator cities at the regional level and support a network dedicated to financing and funding adaptation.

The content will be focusing on Investment planning with a participative approach based on collective intelligence. The goal is also to promote LRT as a collaborative platform for accelerating climate adaptation that will be sustained beyond the project.

3.2.2 Analysis of Scaling Potential

The scaling up process aims to identify the opportunity to ensure the LRT sustainability beyond the project. It is supported by the LRT scope and the level of stakeholder engagement.

- The LRT scope refers to the openness of the LRT towards stakeholders from local/regional/national level and its capacity to attract interests from higher levels for local projects.
- The stakeholder's engagement level refers to the rules and responsibilities distribution among LRT members, the definition of the decision-making process, and what resources are available to sustain LRTs., and what resources are available to sustain LRTs.

Working on both those two pillars will be the main focus in the following months to operationalize LRTs.

The challenges related to LRT implementation have been detailed in D4.5 and are partially resolved.

- Concerns regarding the definition of what an LRT should have been largely addressed through the work carried out by Ramboll under WP4.
- Challenges related to engaging private FIEs persist. Specific efforts by PAs and Facilitators, coordinated by the project lead, are being dedicated tackle this issue across the project.
- Concerns about potential conflicts of interest are being mitigated on a case-by-case basis, with tailored solutions adapted to each local context.

- Regarding the scale and legal form of the LRTs, these issues will be addressed in September through the LRT planning document as part of the second wave of LRTs.
- Ownership of the LRT remains a challenge in each territory and must be addressed individually. The two upcoming consolidation workshops will offer an opportunity for PAs to integrate LRTs into their existing processes and activities.
- The financial sustainability of LRTs remains a concern that needs resolution. As such, as of the production of this report, Ramboll is conducting interviews with international initiatives running similar governance platforms to identify potential solutions.

The main challenge faced by facilitators for LRT development is due to the lack of stakeholder engagement, especially for smaller territories. This challenge is shared across IS, IP, IC development as well as all other tasks within CLIMATEFIT. The consortium decided to provide a response that address this issues at the scale of the project, to avoid overlapping and overloading of facilitators and PAs. For some territories, the chosen solution was to integrate the LRT into existing working groups dedicated to climate adaptation. The PA is responsible for advancing financing and funding issues within these existing structures. The consolidation workshop and the bilateral meeting will provide support to ensure that climate finance is addressed within these groups, and that dedicated events are organized to highlight these issues with the appropriate stakeholders.

The planning of activities scheduled for September 2025 will provide territories with a clearer understanding of expectations and help foster a collective dynamic. It will also serve as a reminder that we are aiming for a co-designed approach, and that the implementation of the LRT should be supported by collective intelligence.

A detailed analysis of success factors and mitigation solutions will be available in future D5.1 "Guidelines to create and expand the LRT" due M38 (October 2026).

4 Synergies with the European Network of local resilience taskforces - EUNLRT

The EUNLRT acts as a platform for knowledge exchange, policy learning, and stakeholder engagement around the design and implementation of bankable climate adaptation solutions. This European network, intents to integrate insights from its different members to strengthen the formulation, consolidation, and potential scaling of LRTs across Europe.

This section outlines how the EUNLRT complements and supports the ongoing work of LRTs, while serving as a strategic dissemination and co-creation mechanism for CLIMATEFIT's overall ambition to mainstream adaptation financing at the local level.

4.1 Overview of the EUNLRT

The EUNLRT is a structured network bringing together public authorities (PAs), Financing and Investment Entities (FIEs), and regional facilitators to foster

dialogue, share practical experiences, and promote investment readiness for local climate adaptation initiatives and projects.

Established within CLIMATEFIT's project, the EUNLRT functions through a series of thematic and interactive EU-wide webinars and peer exchanges. These aim to:

- Disseminate learnings from the experimentation and setup of LRTs,
- Identify barriers and enablers to adaptation financing,
- Mobilize existing initiatives and networks (e.g., Covenant of Mayors, Resilient Cities Network),
- Create visibility for replicable practices and champion stakeholders.

4.2 Linking LRT Consolidation and Scale-Up to the EUNLRT

The relationship between LRT consolidation and the EUNLRT is symbiotic. On one hand, the network draws upon the practical experiences of established LRTs, transforming localized successes into transferable methodologies. For instance, Flanders' multi-level governance model and Alba Iulia's municipal-led approach provide templates for adaptation planning tailored to diverse administrative contexts. On the other hand, the EUNLRT actively supports emerging LRTs by facilitating access to expertise, financing opportunities, and peer learning. This dual function ensures that the scaling process is both evidence-based and adaptive to regional needs.

Collaboration with parallel EU initiatives further enriches this ecosystem. The EUNLRT aligns with the EU Mission on Adaptation to position LRTs as key vehicles for delivering regional resilience goals. Similarly, partnerships with Horizon Europe projects like ARSINOE and IMPETUS enable cross-pollination of methodologies, particularly in integrating nature-based solutions and risk financing mechanisms.

4.3 Summary of insights from the first EU-wide webinars

The first webinar of the European Network of Local Resilience Taskforces (EUNLRT) series took place on 4 March 2025 and represented an important milestone in fostering dialogue, knowledge exchange, and collaboration among the various stakeholders engaged in the development and scaling of Local Resilience Taskforces (LRTs). The session gathered around 60 participants, reflecting a broad diversity of actors involved in climate adaptation and territorial resilience. Among the attendees, there was significant representation from the CLIMATEFIT consortium partners, complemented by public authorities, NGOs and non-profit organizations, academic institutions, and a smaller but notable presence of financial institutions and private sector representatives. The participation of external stakeholders added further value by enriching the discussions with perspectives from outside the project's immediate network.

One of the main objectives of this first session was to create an opportunity for participants to share their expectations regarding the role of the EUNLRT webinars in supporting their work. The feedback gathered during the discussion highlighted several common priorities: the need for practical guidance on implementing LRTs in different governance contexts, access to financing and investment planning strategies, and opportunities for peer-to-peer exchange to

learn directly from the experiences of pilot regions and other territories across Europe.

The agenda of the webinar was jointly prepared by ICLEI and the WCF, who introduced the CLIMATEFIT project and provided an overview of the objectives behind the LRT framework. Building on this introduction, colleagues from ACTIERRA and Ramboll facilitated an engaging panel discussion that explored practical experiences from the field, focusing specifically on the establishment of an LRT in Flanders, Belgium. The discussion featured two key stakeholders: Gert Huybrechts (Financial Representative, Embuilt) and Varnika Srivastava (Public Authority Facilitator, University of Antwerp), who shared valuable insights into the process of forming and operationalizing an LRT in their region. Both panellists highlighted the main challenges encountered, the institutional arrangements that facilitated progress, and the lessons learned so far, offering concrete examples that were highly relevant to participants considering similar processes in their own territories.

Figure 10. First EUNLRT webinar. March 2025. Recording available ([here](#))

Overall, the discussions during the webinar provided several important insights for the further development of the LRT framework. A recurring theme was the necessity of adapting the model to the specific governance structures and institutional contexts of each territory, as participants emphasized that no single blueprint can be universally applied. Another point of discussion was the role of financial institutions and private sector actors. While there was a strong willingness expressed by participants to involve FIEs as early as possible—recognizing their contribution as essential to laying the ground for a robust social innovation process—it was also acknowledged that, in practice, engaging these actors remains highly challenging. Experience shows that their involvement often occurs at later stages of implementation, underlining the need for carefully tailored communication and incentive strategies to secure their participation. Finally, the webinar highlighted the value of establishing structured replication pathways, combining technical support, peer learning, and accessible implementation resources to facilitate the uptake of the LRT model by new regions.

Subsequent webinars are expected to further explore the roles of financial institutions, investment planning, and replication strategies, while progressively building a community of practice around LRT deployment. They will also focus on sharing insights from the leader territories, monitoring the progress of the LRT scale-up, fostering collaboration and peer-to-peer exchanges between the forming LRTs, and, ultimately, assessing the overall state of the LRTs, capturing lessons learned and providing recommendations for future implementation.

Figure 11. EUNLRTs Webinar series

4.4 Use of feedback to inform LRT scaling and formulation

The EUNLRT's webinars, workshops, and stakeholder engagement activities serve as critical platforms not only for fostering interaction between existing LRTs but also for systematizing the scaling process across new regions. These collaborative spaces enable the distillation of practical insights, ensuring that lessons learned from pioneer territories directly inform the formulation and consolidation of LRTs in other regions.

Through structured dialogue, the EUNLRT captures feedback from diverse stakeholders—including public authorities, financial institutions, and civil society—to identify both barriers and success factors in adaptation financing. For example, challenges such as aligning incentives between municipalities and private investors, or opportunities like leveraging EU funding mechanisms, emerge clearly through these exchanges. This collective intelligence is then synthesized into actionable guidance, ensuring that each new LRT benefits from the cumulative experience of the network.

5 Next Steps and Future Outlook

As the CLIMATEFIT project advances, this chapter outlines the critical actions required to consolidate the achievements of LRTs and ensure their long-term impact. Building on the successful establishment and scaling of LRTs across eight European regions, the focus shifts to institutionalizing the model and preparing for sustained implementation beyond the project timeline.

5.1 Finalization of LRT guidelines (linked to T4.1 outcomes)

The development of comprehensive Local Resilience Taskforce (LRT) Implementation Guidelines (scheduled for completion as Deliverable D5.1 in Month 38 – October 2026) represents a central priority for the final phase of the CLIMATEFIT project. These guidelines will distil the lessons learned from both pioneer and scaling regions, offering a standardized yet adaptable framework for establishing and operating LRTs. The content will be structured to support diverse local contexts while maintaining consistency in approach and quality.

Key areas to be addressed include:

- Stakeholder engagement processes and governance structures tailored to multi-actor collaboration.
- Investment planning and financial structuring to support climate adaptation measures.
- Monitoring, evaluation, and reporting mechanisms for tracking LRT progress and impact.

In direct linkage to the outcomes of Task 4.1, the guidelines will integrate insights gathered from regional and local workshops, cross-learning sessions, and EUNLRT webinars. This process ensures that the final document reflects both practical challenges and effective solutions identified during on-the-ground implementation. By embedding these real-world experiences, the guidelines will serve not only as a technical reference but also as a pragmatic tool for replication.

The final version of the LRT Implementation Guidelines will be a cornerstone resource for new cities and regions seeking to establish LRTs, providing clear benchmarks for success and step-by-step pathways for operationalization. In this way, the guidelines will underpin the scaling strategy, enabling a consistent yet flexible approach across Europe.

5.2 Preparation for next EUNLRT webinars

The upcoming EUNLRT webinars will play a pivotal role in consolidating and disseminating the experiences of both pioneer and replication regions. The second and third webinars will be designed as interactive spaces where forming LRTs can share their progress, exchange lessons learned and receive targeted feedback. These sessions will also integrate the perspectives of regions participating in the replication process, ensuring cross-pollination of ideas and fostering stronger alignment in scaling efforts.

The concluding EUNLRT webinar, scheduled for Month 36 (August 2026), will serve as a strategic culmination of the network's activities. It will:

- Showcase territorial achievements and investment outcomes generated by the LRTs.
- Present the finalized LRT Implementation Guidelines and Replication Toolkit to all participants.
- Facilitate peer-to-peer exchanges between pioneer and follower regions to jointly address scaling challenges, identify new opportunities, and strengthen future collaborations.

By combining knowledge-sharing with strategic networking, the webinar series will not only reinforce the visibility of the LRT model but also build momentum for its adoption and institutionalization beyond the lifespan of CLIMATEFIT.

5.3 Suggested pathways for institutionalizing LRTs beyond CLIMATEFIT

Ensuring the long-term sustainability of Local Resilience Taskforces requires moving beyond project-based structures towards mechanisms that are embedded within existing governance, finance, and policy frameworks. The institutionalization process will build on the synergies already identified by CLIMATEFIT with EU-level initiatives, national adaptation strategies, and regional climate action frameworks, leveraging these connections to secure political commitment and operational continuity.

A first pathway involves formal integration of LRTs into local and regional climate governance structures. This could be achieved by designating the LRT as an official coordination body within municipal or regional administrations, ensuring it has a defined mandate, budgetary line, and decision-making authority. Such integration will also facilitate alignment with existing climate adaptation and resilience planning processes, creating consistency between LRT priorities and statutory policy objectives.

A second pathway focuses on embedding the LRT concept within regional and national adaptation funding programmes. By positioning LRTs as the recognized mechanism for developing and coordinating investment-ready adaptation projects, they can become the natural entry point for financing streams, both from public sources (national adaptation funds, EU cohesion policy instruments) and private capital channels.

A third pathway seeks to institutionalize the EUNLRT network as a long-term peer learning and coordination mechanism. The intended goal is to secure the network's legacy by transitioning its stewardship to a sustainable structure beyond the project's lifecycle, whose mandate and capabilities are aligned with its objectives. This future transition is seen as critical for ensuring the network's sustainability and continued evolution beyond the CLIMATEFIT funding period. By maintaining and expanding the relationships forged during the project—between pioneer regions, replication sites, and thematic experts—an institutionalized EUNLRT would serve as a vital, ongoing source of technical support, knowledge exchange, and innovation for local and regional authorities across Europe.

Finally, CLIMATEFIT's institutionalization strategy will emphasize the cultivation of "LRT champions" across public authorities, Financial Institutions, and community actors. These champions, identified during the project, can act as advocates for the LRT model, supporting its integration into broader climate resilience agendas and helping to expand the network beyond the initial eight taskforces.

Through these pathways—grounded in political alignment, financial integration, network continuity, and stakeholder leadership—the LRT framework can transition from a time-bound project deliverable to a sustainable governance and investment model capable of driving local climate resilience well beyond the duration of CLIMATEFIT.

6 References

Cajaiba-Santana G (2014) Social innovation: Moving the field forward. A conceptual framework. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 82: 42–51.

The CLIMATEFIT project aims to support EU territories in their just and transformational journey toward climate resilience by bridging the finance gap, providing critical insight and building the capacities of (i) Public Authorities (PAs) to identify, orchestrate and attract various public and private financing sources and (ii) Financing & Investment Entities (FIEs) to identify and access resilient investment opportunities. CLIMATEFIT opens a significant opportunity to foster innovative resilience investments in vulnerable EU territories and to boost competitiveness and EU leadership in a growing market. The project will build on a deep understanding of existing initiatives to sustain systemic and catalytic resilience investments by engaging its Technical Partners, PAs and FIEs in the co-creation of twenty innovative investment strategies, ten concrete and scalable investment plans and four bankable transformational investment cases, increasing the bankability of resilient project pipelines across a diversity of scales, financing gaps, contexts, barriers to financing, climate risks and vulnerabilities, biogeographical regions, adaptive capacities and maturity regarding climate change represented from its twenty case studies grouped in three clusters: Northwestern, Eastern and Southern.

